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FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF RASHTRIYA GRAMIN VIKASH NIDHI (NORTH EAST) MICROFINANCE LTD

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ABSTRACT

Rashtriya Gramin Vikash Nidhi (North East) Microfinance Ltd is an organisation providing microfinance to the poor in this region. The broad objective of the paper is to study the financial performance of the concern for the period of six years. The study is based on secondary sources of data. The secondary data has been collected from annual report of RGVN (NE) MFL. The sample size of the study is six years. The period of six years from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is known as reference period of the study. The study makes use of statistical tools such as annual growth rate (AGR) and compound annual growth rate (CAGR), Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test. The CAGR of income from operation of the concern during the study period is more as compared to other income. The hypothesis test proves that there is no significant difference between growth rate between income from operation and other income of RGVN (NE). The compound growth rate of financial expenses is higher than other expenses. The hypothesis test examines that there is no significant difference in growth rate of classification of total expenditure of RGVN (NE). The compound growth of non-current assets is less than current assets. The hypothesis test examines that there is no significant difference between growth rate between non-current assets and current assets of RGVN (NE). The CAGR of current liabilities is higher than non-current liabilities. The hypothesis test proves that there is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current liabilities and current liabilities of concern.

Keywords: Income from operation, other income, Current Asset, Current Liabilities, Total Expenditure, Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test, Kruskal-Wallis Test.

INTRODUCTION

Rashtriya Gramin Vikash Nidhi (North East) Microfinance Ltd, a public limited company, is a registered non-banking financial company (NBFC) with a clear vision to serve the entire North Eastern Region impacting 5 lakh clients by the year 2017 and facilitate better access to health, education and livelihood opportunities. Headquartered in Guwahati, RGVN (NE) MFL as on 31/03/2017 has a network of 139 branches in seven north eastern states viz. Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Tripura, West Bengal and Sikkim covering around 4.08 lakh borrowers with loan outstanding of Rs. 688.32 crore and on time repayment of 98.20 percent. Microfinance is recognized as a tool to alleviate poverty and RGVN (NE) MFL's effort to convert this into a possibility in the north eastern region has been achieved through hand-holding of investors both Indian and Overseas. Apart from this, it has partnered with leading banks and financial institutions for availing debt funds and on lending to the clients across branch its network (www.rgvnnemfl.com).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Valde, Suresh (2011) made a study on Performance of Non Banking Financial Companies in India. In the paper he concluded that the deceleration of growth in expenditure of 1211 companies is higher than the income growth

due to growth in interest payment. A substantial portion of fund raised during the 2008-09 was in the form of borrowings. Other significant portion of funds was in the form of raising fresh capital from the capital market. Major portion of the funds raised during the year was deployed as loans and advances in the credit market. Mohan, Brij (2014) conducted study on Non Banking Financial Companies in India: Types, Needs, Challenges and Importance in Financial Inclusion. It was mentioned in the paper that NBFCs can truly become game changers provided they exhibit the requisite nimbleness and innovative zeal in reaching a complete suite of financial products together with their current product offerings, to the common man. Das, S.K. (2016) undertook study on Performance and Growth of Non-Banking Financial Companies as compared to Banks in India. In the paper he concluded that the NBFCs have been growing at a steady rate and its growth rate is far better than that of banking sector. Proportion of credit provided by the NBFCs to infrastructure is far better than that of banks during the study period. Hence, the contribution of NBFC sector to capital formation as well as overall economic growth has been increasing at a higher rate than that of banks. Kaushal, H.R. (2016) made study on Impact of Non –banking Financial Companies in Indian Economy Growth. In the paper it was concluded that NBFCs are the perfect or even better alternatives to the conventional banks for meeting various financial requirements of a financial enterprise. They offer quick and efficient services without working one to go through the complex rigmarole of conventional banking facilities. Singh, K.R. (2014) conducted study on Growth and Development of Non-banking Financial Companies in India. The paper focuses on areas evolution, growth and development of NBFCs, regulatory authority and supervision of NBFCs. He mentioned that contribution made by these NBFCs in the economic growth as well as meeting the credit needs of the economy is needed to be appreciated.

Based on the above literature, it has been observed that all studies are devoted to non banking financial companies in general. But these studies lack one specific non banking financial company. The study has been undertaken keeping in mind the need of the study in this area.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The RGVN (NE) MFL is an organisation providing microfinance to the poor in this region. The viability of the concern relies on its good financial performance. The present study makes an attempt to concentrate on financial performance of the organisation for the period of six years.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of the research is i) to study the growth of income from operation and other income over the period of six years, ii) to study the growth of various expenses of concern over the period, iii) to study the growth of non-current liabilities and current liabilities the over period and iv) to study the growth of non-current assets and current assets over the period.

HYPOTHESES FRAMED

Ho1: There is no significant difference between growth rate of income from operation and other income of RGVN (NE) during the study period.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the growth rate of classification of total expenditure of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Ho3: There is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current liabilities and current liabilities of RGVN (NE) over the period.

Ho 4: There is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current assets and current assets of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

METHODOLOGY

The scope of the study covers the financial performance of concern for a specified period of time. The study includes income from operation, other income, financial expenses, personal expenses, administration and other expenses, depreciation, non-current liabilities, current liabilities, non-current assets and current assets etc. The present study is descriptive and analytical in nature. The study is based on secondary sources of data. The secondary data has been collected from annual report of RGVN (NE) MFL. Besides, other sources of secondary data have also been obtained from referred journal to have idea about conceptual framework. The sample size of the study is six years. The period of six years from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is known as reference period of the study. The study makes use of descriptive statistics such as annual growth rate (AGR) and compound annual growth rate (CAGR) to analyze the data. Inferential statistics of non parametric tests viz. Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test and Kruskal-Wallis Test have been employed to draw inference on hypothesis framed for the study. Such type of test is appropriate for small number of sample size below ten.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The measurement for financial performance of the RGVN (NE) MFL has been analyzed in this portion. The parameters viz. income from operation, other income, financial expenses, personal expenses, administrative and other expenses, depreciation, non-current liabilities, current liabilities, non-current assets and current assets of financial performance of the concern are discussed below:

Table1: Growth of Income of the RGVN over a period (Rs. in thousand)

Year	Income from Operation		Other income	
	Amount	Growth Rate	Amount	Growth Rate
2010-11	87672		5417	
2011-12	206789	135.86	7929	46.37
2012-13	283596	37.14	11655	46.99
2013-14	332297	17.17	2598	-77.71
2014-15	425417	28.02	5496	111.55
2015-16	806482	89.57	1184	-78.46
CAGR	44.75		-22.39	

Source: Annual Report of RGVN (NE)

The annual growth of income from operation of the concern in 2011-12 is 135.86 percent (Table 1). It goes up to 37.14 percent in 2012-13 which continues to increase to 17.17 percent in next year. It increases to 28.02 percent and 89.57 percent in two consecutive years. The CAGR of income from operation during the period from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is 44.75 percent. The growth rate of other income of the concern in 2011-12 is 46.37 percent. It increases slightly to 46.99 percent in 2012-13 which declines to 77.17 percent in next year. In 2014-15 it goes up to 111.55 percent and it declines to 78.46 percent in next year. The CAGR of other income over the study period is -22.39 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference between growth rate of income from operation and other income of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test of growth of total Income of RGVN (NE)

Year	Income from Operation		Other income	
	Growth Rate	Rank	Growth Rate	Rank
2011-12	135.86	10	46.37	6
2012-13	37.14	5	46.99	7
2013-14	17.17	3	-77.71	2
2014-15	28.02	4	111.55	9
2015-16	89.57	8	-78.46	1
Total		30		25

Source: Computed Figure

Inference on Hypothesis

It is inferred that the T value (30) is greater than T_L (17) and less than T_U for the growth of income from operation and other income at 5 percent significance level (Table 2). It proves that there is no significant difference between growth rate of income from operation and other income of RGVN (NE) over the study period. Thus, null hypothesis can be accepted.

Table 3: Growth of Various Expenses of the RGVN over a period (Rs. in thousand)

Year	Financial Expenses	Personal Expenses	Admin. And Other expenses	Depreciation
2010-11	41655	28367	7167	851
2011-12	84555 (102.99)	64362 (126.89)	15571 (117.26)	2328 (173.56)
2012-13	126204 (49.26)	70026 (08.8)	23886 (53.40)	2108 (-9.45)
2013-14	150121 (18.95)	86253 (23.17)	23967 (0.34)	2385 (13.14)
2014-15	160384 (06.84)	92808 (07.60)	50225 (109.56)	4422 (85.41)
2015-16	371985 (131.93)	128030 (37.95)	41123 (-18.12)	4344 (-1.76)
CAGR	44.04	28.55	33.80	31.22

Source: Annual Report of RGVN (NE)

Financial expenses of the concern register a growth of 102.99 percent in 2011-12 (Table 3). It increases steeply to 49.26 percent in 2012-13 which continues to go up to 18.95 percent and 6.84 percent in two consecutive years. In 2015-16 it increases steeply to 131.93 percent. The CAGR of financial expenses during the period from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is 44.04 percent. The growth rate of personal expenses in 2011-12 is 126.89 percent. It increases to 8.8 percent in 2012-13 which goes up to 23.17 percent in next year. The upward trend of growth continues to 7.60 percent and 37.95 percent in next two succeeding years (2014-15 and 2015-16). The CAGR of personal expenses over the study period is 28.55 percent. The administration and other expenses register a growth rate of 117.26 percent which increases to 53.40 percent and 0.34 percent in next two succeeding years. It goes up steeply to 109.56 percent in 2014-15 and it goes down to 18.12 percent in next year. The CAGR of administrative and other expenses over the period of six year is 33.80 percent. The growth rate of depreciation in 2011-12 is 173.56 percent. It decreases to 9.45 percent in 2012-13 which goes up to 13.14 percent in next year. The steep upward trend of growth continues to 85.41 percent in succeeding year and it declines to 1.76 percent in 2015-16. The CAGR of depreciation over the study period is 31.22 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the growth rate of classification of total expenditure of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Table 4: Kruskal-Wallis Test of growth of Total Expenditure of RGVN (NE)

Year	Financial Exp		Personal Exp		Adm./Other Exp		Depreciation	
	Growth	Rank	Growth	Rank	Growth	Rank	Growth	Rank
2011-12	102.99	15	126.89	18	117.26	17	173.56	20
2012-13	49.26	12	08.80	7	53.40	13	-09.45	2
2013-14	18.95	9	23.17	10	00.34	4	13.14	8
2014-15	06.84	5	07.60	6	109.56	16	85.41	14
2015-16	131.93	19	37.95	11	-18.12	1	-1.76	3
Total		60		52		51		47

Source: Computed Figure

Inference on Hypothesis

It is inferred from Table 4 that the calculated value of W for total expenditure (0.38) is less than the table value of chi-square (5.99 at 5 percent level). Hence, null hypothesis can be accepted. It proves that there is no significant difference in the growth rate of classification of total expenditure of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Table 5: Growth of Liabilities of the RGVN over a period (Rs. in thousand)

Year	Non Current Liabilities		Current Liabilities	
	Amount	Growth Rate	Amount	Growth Rate
2010-11	616653		169957	
2011-12	956553	55.21	113697	-33.10
2012-13	564885	-40.95	685397	502.83
2013-14	471384	-16.55	625485	-08.74
2014-15	746529	58.37	2721250	335.06
2015-16	2467787	230.57	5715595	110.03
CAGR	26		79.66	

Source: Annual Report of RGVN (NE)

The annual growth of non-current liabilities of the concern in 2011-12 is 55.21 percent (Table 5). It declines to -40.95 percent in 2012-13 which continues to go down to 16.55 percent in next year. In 2014-15 it increases to 58.37 percent and it goes up steeply to 230.57 percent in next year. The CAGR of non-current liabilities during the period from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is 26 percent. The growth rate of current liabilities of the concern in 2011-12 is -33.10 percent. It increases steeply to 502.83 percent in 2012-13 which declines to -8.74 percent in next year. In 2014-15 it goes up steeply to 335.06 percent and it continues to increase to 110.3 percent in next year. The CAGR of current liabilities over the study period is 79.66 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho3: There is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current liabilities and current liabilities of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Table 6: Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test of growth of Total Liabilities of RGVN (NE)

Year	Non Current Liabilities		Current Liabilities	
	Growth Rate	Rank	Growth Rate	Rank
2011-12	55.21	5	-33.10	2
2012-13	-40.95	1	502.83	10
2013-14	-16.55	3	08.74	4
2014-15	58.37	6	335.06	9
2015-16	230.57	8	110.03	7
Total		23		32

Source: Computed Figure

Inference on Hypothesis

It is inferred that the T value (23) is greater than T_L (17) and less than T_U for the growth of non-current liabilities and current liabilities at 5 percent significance level (Table 6). It examines that there is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current liabilities and current liabilities of RGVN (NE) over the study period. Thus, null hypothesis can be accepted.

Table 7: Growth of Various Assets of the RGVN over a period (Rs. in thousand)

Year	Non Current Assets		Current Assets	
	Amount	Growth Rate	Amount	Growth Rate
2010-11	859446		28395	
2011-12	1155735	34.47	80125	182.18
2012-13	142789	-87.65	1345420	1579.15
2013-14	125286	-12.26	1326569	-1.40
2014-15	765853	511.28	2721250	105.13
2015-16	1533039	100.17	5715595	110.03
CAGR	10.13		142.09	

Source: Annual Report of RGVN (NE)

The non-current assets of the concern register a growth of 34.47 percent in 2011-12 (Table7). It declines steeply to -87.25 percent in 2012-13 which continues to go down to 12.26 percent and 511.28 percent in succeeding year. In 2015-16 it increases to 100.17 percent. The CAGR of non-current assets during the period from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is 10.13 percent. The growth rate of current asset in 2011-12 is 182.18 percent. It increases steeply to 1579.15 percent in 2012-13 which goes down to 1.40 percent in next year. It increases to 105.13 percent and 110.03 percent in next two succeeding years (2014-15 and 2015-16). The CAGR of current asset over the study period is 142.09 percent.

Testing of Hypothesis

Ho 4: There is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current assets and current assets of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

Table 8: Mann-Whitney-Wilcoxon Test of growth of Total Assets of RGVN (NE)

Year	Non Current Assets		Current Assets	
	Growth Rate	Rank	Growth Rate	Rank
2011-12	34.47	4	182.18	8
2012-13	-87.65	1	1579.15	10
2013-14	12.26	3	-1.40	2
2014-15	511.28	9	105.13	6
2015-16	100.17	5	110.03	7
Total		22		33

Source: Computed Figure

Inference on Hypothesis

It is inferred that the T value (22) is greater than T_L (17) and less than T_U for the growth of non-current assets and current assets at 5 percent significance level (Table 8). It examines that there is no significant difference between growth rate between non-current assets and current assets of RGVN (NE) over the study period. Thus, null hypothesis can be accepted.

CONCLUSION

The CAGR of income from operation of the concern during the period from 2010-11 to 2015-16 is more (44.75) as compared to other income (-22.39). The hypothesis test proves that there is no significant difference between growth rate between income from operation and other income of RGVN (NE) over the study period. The compound growth rate of financial expenses (44.04) over the period is higher than other expenses viz. personal expenses (28.55), administrative and other expenses (33.80) and depreciation (31.22). The hypothesis test examines that there is no significant difference in growth rate of classification of total expenditure of RGVN (NE) over the study period. The compound growth of non-current assets is less (10.13) than current assets (142.09). The hypothesis test examines that there is no significant difference between growth rate between non-current assets and current assets of RGVN (NE) over the study period. The CAGR of current liabilities over the study period is higher (79.66) than non-current liabilities (26). The hypothesis test proves that there is no significant difference between growth rate of non-current liabilities and current liabilities of RGVN (NE) over the study period.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study has got certain limitations. First, the present study fully relies on the secondary sources of data provided in the annual report of the concern. Secondly, the study is restricted to the period of six years only.

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